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CONNECTIONS BETWEEN HYPERCUBES, DNF AND HAMMING DISTANCE¹

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Abstract. *We propose some advanced concepts from discrete math and coding theory for amplifying students' understanding of the matter. In this paper, we use the bijection between the points of the hypercube, and the minterms of the disjunctive normal form of a binary function. This allows us to introduce the concepts of: binary n -tuples, Hamming distance, paths in graphs, and graph coloring, among others.*

Keywords: *distance, DNF, graphs, hypercube, minimization.*

I. Introduction

Sometimes when teaching a college level Mathematics classes like discrete mathematics, linear algebra, etc. one faces challenges explaining complex concepts to the students. For example, the Quine-McCluskey algorithm and Karnaugh diagrams are such hard to grasp topics. In order to mitigate such hurdles, we propose to use advanced concepts from discrete mathematics and coding theory that can increase students' understanding of the matter and at the same time encourage pupils to delve deeper in subjects interconnections. In this paper, we propose to explore the bijection between the points of the hypercube, and the minterms of the disjunctive normal form of a binary function. Using this bijection, we can introduce the concepts of: binary n -tuples, Hamming distance, paths in graphs, and graph coloring, among others.

This work is organized as follows: We start with hypercubes and Hamming distance in Section II. Next, we continue with disjunctive normal forms, the sums of products

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expansion representation in Section III, and the Karnaugh diagram in the next section. We finish with the last two sections dedicated to the main ideas of this paper: in dimension 3 -- the cube graph coloring for DNF minimization in Section V, and in higher dimensions in Section VI.

II. Hypercubes and Hamming distance

The **hypercube** Q_n is the graph whose vertices are n -tuples with entries in $\{0,1\}$ and two vertices are connected if and only if their corresponding n -tuples differ in exactly one position. For example, in Q_4 the vertices 1001 and 1101 are connected, whereas 1010 and 1001 are not.

The hypercube Q_3 (which is the regular cube) is depicted in Figure 1. Note that the vertices are labeled with their corresponding binary triples and two vertices are connected if and only if they differ in exactly one position.

Figure 1. The cube Q_3

Define the **Hamming distance** between two binary n -tuples $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) \in Q_n$ as the number of position they differ, $d(x, y) = |x_i \neq y_i : 1 \leq i \leq n|$. For example the distance between 1011 and 0110 is 3 since their

first, second and fourth coordinates are different and the third one is the same.

Looking again at Figure 1, the distance between two vertices $d(x, y)$ can be viewed as the number of edges (in the shortest path) we have to traverse in the graph in order to walk from x to y . For more information on graphs and paths we direct the reader to [2].

Thus, to walk from 000 to 111 (triples with distance 3), one can choose multiple paths for example $000 \rightarrow 100 \rightarrow 110 \rightarrow 111$ or $000 \rightarrow 001 \rightarrow 101 \rightarrow 111$ flipping consecutively different positions, but always the shortest path should be 3, since we have to flip exactly 3 positions. This means that, for an arbitrary vertex $x \in Q_n$: all 1-distance vertices are those connected by an edge of the cube; all 2-distance vertices (a total of 3) are those on opposite end of the cube's face diagonals; all 3-distance vertices (again a total of 3) are in the opposite end of the cube's diagonals connected with x .

III. Disjunctive normal form

Let $\mathbb{B} = \{0,1\}$ be the Boolean set. Given a Boolean function $f: \mathbb{B}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{B}$ we say that it is in **disjunctive normal form (DNF)** if it is a disjunction of one or more conjunctions of one or more literals. A DNF formula is in full disjunctive normal form if each of its variables appears exactly once in every conjunction. The only propositional operators in DNF are conjunctions (\wedge), disjunctions (\vee), and not (\neg). The not operator can only be used as part of a literal, which means that it can only precede a propositional variable. Using the **support** of a Boolean function which is defined as follows: $\text{Supp}(f) = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{B} : f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = 1\}$ it's well

known that by denoting $x_i^{a_i} = \begin{cases} 0, & x_i \neq a_i \\ 1, & x_i = a_i \end{cases}$, the DNF is given by

the formula $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \bigvee_{(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \text{Supp}(f)} x_1^{a_1} x_2^{a_2} \cdots x_n^{a_n}$, where

the main disjunction is applied only to all vectors $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \text{Supp}(f)$. The corresponding term $x_1^{a_1} x_2^{a_2} \dots x_n^{a_n}$ for every $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \text{Supp}(f)$ is called its **minterm**. More information on the subject can be found for example in [1].

The following general problem is often considered: Given a Boolean function in DNF, how to find a representation with the least possible number of summands. This is the so-called **SOPE (sums of products expansion) representation** of Boolean functions. The well-known Quine and McCluskey algorithm (see [3] and [4]), which is presented in most discrete mathematics classes, is the defacto standard when we have at least 4 variables. For small n the minimization, that is the transformation from DNF to SOPE can be done using a Karnaugh diagram.

All methods are based in the observation that for every variable x_i we have $x_i K \vee \overline{x_i} K = K$.

Given a Boolean function $f(x, y, z)$ in DNF it's obvious that the DNF contains some subset of all eight possible minterms, and if (as in our example) two minterms differ in a single variable, we may simplify by adding these minterms and deleting the variable. This is based on the reversed distribution rule

$$(1) \quad x_i K \vee \overline{x_i} K = (x_i \vee \overline{x_i}) K = K.$$

Notice that in terms of Hamming distance two minterms differ in a single variable if the distance between the two n -tuples is exactly 1.

IV. The Karnaugh diagram

With the Karnaugh diagram we map the eight possible minterms in a rectangular array in such a way that neighboring fields differ by a single variable (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The Karnaugh diagram for 3 variables

In the Karnaugh diagram every square represents a minterm corresponding to the conjunction of this square's terms. For example, the (2,3) square has row \bar{x} and columns \bar{y}, \bar{z} thus giving the optimized conjunction $\bar{x} \bar{y} \bar{z}$.

To use the diagram, we mark with the number 1 every square that is in the support of f . We have to look at the diagram as a cyclical structure, that means that the squares in the last row (column) are neighboring the corresponding squares in first row (column). The main advantage of the Karnaugh diagram is that the minterms that can be optimized using (1) are neighbors, and we only need to look at the 1×2 , 2×1 or bigger rectangles that occur but only if it has the number $2^l, l \geq 1$ as its face.

V. Using hypercube graphs coloring for DNF minimization

Example 1: Let $f(x, y, z) = \bar{x}\bar{y}z \vee \bar{x}yz \vee x\bar{y}\bar{z} \vee x\bar{y}z \vee xyz$.

In this case we have the diagram (Figure 3) where the 1's form two red rectangles which create an actual square that forms the variable z as an applicant. On the other hand, the two 1's marked in green form the other applicant in the SOPE, that is $x\bar{y}$. Thus the minimized DNF is $f(x, y, z) = x\bar{y} \vee z$.

Figure 3. The Karnaugh diagram for Example 1

We propose, instead of the Karnaugh diagram, to use the hypercube and mark the vertices corresponding to the minterms that are in the DNF. Next, we have to look at all edges that have marked endings, all squares (faces of the cube) with four marked corners and so on. Thus, the coloring of the cube graph for the DNF from Example 1 is given in Figure 4. We can see that we have 5 edges of which 4 forms the face of the cube corresponding to the term z .

Figure 4. The cube graph for Example 1

This can also be derived from the coordinates of the 4 vertices (or the path): $(001) \rightarrow (011) \rightarrow (111) \rightarrow (101)$. Note that this path connects neighbors having Hamming distance of 1. Next, the edge $(100) \rightarrow (101)$ leads to the optimized (10) , which is $x\bar{y}$.

VI. Higher number of variables

It's hard for humans to picture higher dimensions but the hypercube Q_4 (here we have four variables x, y, z, t) can be represented by its third-dimension projection Figure 5). If we

color the vertices of Q_4 that correspond to the midterms of given DNF we have the following options:

- **edges:** for example, the edge $1011 \rightarrow 1111$ differs in position 2 only. Thus, it will minimize to $1_11 = xzt$;
- **faces:** for example, the square defined by the path $0110 \rightarrow 1110 \rightarrow 1100 \rightarrow 0100$ will cancel 2 variables and minimize to $_1_0 = y\bar{t}$;
- **cubes:** for example, the cube defined by the path $1000 \rightarrow 1001 \rightarrow 1011 \rightarrow 1010 \rightarrow 0010 \rightarrow 0011 \rightarrow 0010 \rightarrow 0000$ will cancel 3 variables and is minimized to $_0_ = \bar{y}$;
- **the hypercube:** In this case all vertices of the hypercube will be colored and we have all 16 minterms (i.e., the complete DNF) and the minimization leads to $____ = 1$.

Figure 5. The hypercube Q_4

The paragraph above clearly explains why when using the Karnaugh diagram, even when we have more than 3 variables, we are only looking at rectangle that have $2^l, l \geq 1$ filled squares with ones.

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